

POSSIBILITIES OF DEVELOPING SOCIAL COMPETENCE IN FUTURE EDUCATORS

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Abstract. *This article focuses on the issues of improving the professional competence of innovative educational environment for the development of social relations in students. In addition, at the same time, it discusses the current innovative educational environment in Uzbekistan and the important aspect of the innovative educational environment for students.*

Key words: *innovative education, student, professional competence, creative thinking, innovative processes, teacher, pedagogical process.*

Аннотация. *Данная статья посвящена вопросам повышения профессиональной компетентности инновационной образовательной среды для развития социальных отношений у студентов. Кроме того, одновременно обсуждается современная инновационная образовательная среда в Узбекистане и важный аспект инновационной образовательной среды для студентов.*

Ключевые слова: *Инновационное образование, студент, профессиональная компетентность, творческое мышление, инновационные процессы, педагог, педагогический процесс.*

The current stage of the development of the society of independent Uzbekistan is characterized by a rapid change in technology, which leads to the formation of a new educational system that includes constant renewal. The success of continuous education depends on the ability of all subjects of the educational system to maintain competitiveness, and its most important conditions are personal characteristics such as activity, initiative, creative thinking and the ability to find non-standard solutions. Improving the foundations of social competence development is one of the urgent pedagogical problems of today.

This showed that it is necessary to decide on a scientific approach to the improvement of the pedagogical foundations of the development of the professional competence of the teachers of the educational organization. The relevance of studying the problem of formation of social competences in future educators is related to the high pace of development of society and the growing demands for social competence of its members. Social competences are manifested in the exchange of information to influence the results of the actions and activities of others, as well as to assess one's own position, which affects the formation of interests and behavior of social subjects. Pre-school education is a legacy for the future. The value of this wealth is so great that it makes a person spiritually rich and fills his heart with happiness and divine light. There is no one in the world without a teacher. Whether he is a government leader, a great scientist, a doctor, a popular writer, or a handpicker, everyone will have a teacher and a guide who lights the path of life. The greatest duty of a teacher is to train intelligent, capable, well-educated students who will benefit the people. In society, a pedagogue (educator) performs honorable and responsible tasks, firstly, to educate the growing generation, and secondly, to provide all-round knowledge to

our hardworking people. An educator fulfills the important and proud and at the same time responsible task of raising the young generation to become worthy children of our nation. The political maturity of an educator helps to realize his responsibility to the people and society for the quality of children's education, to take a creative approach to solving educational and educational tasks, to constantly activate his skills, and to help his colleagues to grow at work. An educator should know the life of the country where he lives, understand the factors of nature and society, and be socially active. In any society, it is hard and hard work to bring up a competent generation, bring it to adulthood and direct it to a certain profession. This hard work is the product of continuous education and training. Education is a pedagogical activity organized between the teacher and the students. It is a regular and systematic influence on the individual in order to improve the student in accordance with a certain goal. is a process of intensive activity directed at ideologies. On the basis of education, the mind of the student is formed, his spiritual wealth and emotions are developed, moral habits are formed that are necessary to find his place in social life, and serve to properly organize interaction with people. for us it is a matter of life or death, or salvation - or disaster, or happiness - or joy" - this is the truth that corresponds to the upbringing of representatives of all nations.

A pedagogue-educator influences children in everyday life, in games, training, joint work and dealings with them. He should carefully study each child, know his personal characteristics, abilities, show pedagogical sensitivity, honestly evaluate children's behavior and work results, be able to provide timely help to them, and be interested in their family situation. One of the main qualities of a modern educator is his devotion to his profession, his ideological conviction, his love for his profession, and his endless devotion to this profession, which distinguishes the educator from other professions. One of the important requirements for a pedagogue-educator is that he must have thoroughly mastered his subject and its methodology. This raises the reputation of the pedagogue-educator. One of the important qualities and requirements of a teacher's profession is to love children, to be interested in their lives, to respect each person. Only a person who loves a child and can mobilize all his strength and knowledge to raise children to become loyal citizens of the great country in the future can be a real teacher and pedagogue. Loving children makes the difficult work of a pedagogue attractive and easy. Educator's attitude towards children in pedagogy is equal to respect for the person being educated and demands on him. This attitude instills confidence in the child towards the teacher, allows the educator to become a real spiritual mentor of children. The success of a teacher's activity also depends on the availability of pedagogical skills. Pedagogical ability is the basis for achieving pedagogical skills. Pedagogical ability includes: pedagogical observation, pedagogical imagination, distribution of attention, organizational ability and pedagogical behavior. Pedagogical abilities are formed in the process of pedagogical activity, as well as in the process of preparing him for this activity. Pedagogical skill is the art of high-level and continuous improvement of education of the young generation. The personal characteristics of educators in the preschool education organization are determined by their tasks in the children's team, their dedication in their work, love of children, interest in the child's perspective. In general, educators working in a preschool educational organization should also have the following psycho-physiological characteristics: strong health, common sense, physical strength, willpower, endurance, hard work, enthusiasm, bravery. enthusiasm etc. They should also be able to think constructively, analytically and creatively. They need constructive thinking for rational development and fair organization of work, analytical thinking is needed to monitor the child's

development of work and drawing skills and analyze their results, and finally, creative thinking is every step in the process of professional activity. It is very necessary to independently solve a task or task and to see their perspectives. In addition, in this process, the speech culture of coaches and educators is of special importance.

Educator's creativity and competence:

1) A creative, creative approach to the organization of the education and training process in the pedagogue, development of abilities and skills to positively solve existing pedagogical problems;

2) It sheds light on the basics of professional training based on the formation and gradual development of the skills of a positive, independent approach to the acquisition of educational materials, the ability to advance new, creative and creative ideas in the performance of educational tasks, the development of personal creativity at different ages learns to develop according to the characteristics of the stages.

The creativity and competence of an educator consists in creative teaching, competent upbringing and development of a person.

The general nature of the educator's creativity and competence is revealed on the basis of a number of concepts that represent his conceptual states. They consist of:

Creativity is a person's activity that determines the importance and usefulness of a particular innovation and its result; A creative person is a person who can successfully implement the creative process and has clear creative results (products);

A creative person is a person who demonstrates creativity as a process or result, is inclined to approach solving problems in non-standard ways, is capable and ready to organize unique actions, promote innovations, create creative products; A creative person is a person who realizes objective creativity both as a process and as a result and can create creative products at the level of requirements; Training of a creative person is the content of formation and development of stable creative qualities in a person in the process of teaching creativity and self-creative expression; Creativity - the result of the activity or activity of a social subject whose novelty, importance and usefulness is recognized by society or a specific group; Education of a creative person - formation and development of a person with creative ideas, skills and qualifications for their implementation based on the decision-making and enrichment of professional and creative activity experiences; Professional-creative activity - the activity of a specialist describing the success of the creative solution of professional issues, innovative behavior; Creative tasks - a system of problems aimed at solving problematic situations based on a systematic analysis;

Professional opportunity:

- 1) professional competence, qualification;
- 2) mastering the basics of the methodology of professional creativity;
- 3) level of formation of creative thinking;
- 4) development of professional and creative ability and personal qualities

Creative thinking is a type of thinking that represents the organization of the creative process and the prediction of creative results (products). Creative ability is an individual characteristic of a person that determines the possibility of organizing creative activity and ensuring the achievement of its results. Creative ability is an individual characteristic that is manifested in the successful implementation of creative activity and evaluation of its results.

Self-creative activation - full manifestation and development of one's potential in creative

activities. The professional and creative potential of pedagogues is seen in the positive resolution of professional issues and the appropriate assessment of their solutions. Educator competence. The concept of "competence" entered the field of education as a result of psychological research. Therefore, competence is "how a specialist behaves in unconventional situations, unexpected situations, engages in communication, takes a new way in relations with opponents, performs ambiguous tasks, uses conflicting information, consistently develops and "ownership of a plan of action in complex processes". In modern society, innovation is not only a condition for the existence of the economy, turning it into a socially oriented economy that works for people, but is also becoming the most important universal factor of controlled social development.

The main functions of innovative activity include changing the components of the pedagogical process, reflecting the content, goals, content, forms, methods, technologies, educational tools, management systems, etc. of education. At the same time, almost all researchers agree that not all types of research can be considered innovative, because innovations are purposeful, meaningful changes. Without ignoring these changes, it can be seen that the role of the innovative educational environment in improving the professional competence of students in developing their social relations is incomparable.

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